

TWENTY-TWO YEARS AFTER THE MONTERREY CONSENSUS: ISSUES, CHALLENGES, AND PROSPECTS

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Abstract: The Monterrey Consensus, a framework for discussion on development finance between the global North and South, is at the core of commitments to address the problem of development in Africa. This paper attempts to assess the performance of the Monterrey Consensus over a period of approximately 20 years. It argues that Africa has experienced slight economic growth in the area of external debt relief since the adoption of the consensus in March 2002, although much work remains to be done in the areas of mobilizing international finance for development and promoting international trade policies. The paper concludes that a genuine commitment to the principles of the consensus can adequately address the problems of economic development and lay a solid foundation for a brighter future for Africa and Africans.

Keywords: Consensus, Development, Framework, Monterrey, Prospects

Introduction

The Monterrey Consensus was adopted by Heads of States and Government in March 2002 as a major framework for discussion on development finance by states in the global North and South. This was a turning point that produced a breakthrough on the issue of official development assistance, with substantial new pledges and a major change in attitude.¹

The adoption of this international commitment was an important measure for the African states in mobilizing domestic and external financial resources for poverty reduction and economic growth. March 2024 marked 22 years of operation of the Consensus, and what readily comes to the mind of many enlightened Africans is the extent to which the goals and objectives have been achieved in its six core areas.² Various measures have been geared toward African development, including the 2005 World Summit Outcome, the 2005 Paris Declaration, and the 2005 G8 Gleneagles Summit declaration. Moreover, since the dawn of the new millennium, G8 member states have paid attention to development issues affecting Africa in their various summits. Of all these commitments, the 2005 G8 Gleneagles Summit was the first comprehensive and decisive effort to address

¹<http://www.un.org/esa/ffd/documents/Building%20on%20Monterrey.pdf> (Accessed: April 13, 2023).

²Karjomuise, K., Osakwe, P., Shimeles, A., & Verick, S. (Eds.) *The Monterrey Consensus and Development in Africa: Progress, Challenges and Way Forward: The UN Economic Commission for Africa*, 2007, p. 3.

Africa's economic crisis.³ In this measure, the G8 states recognized the need to substantially increase the ODA to Africa to enhance the prospect of economic development. In this regard, the G8 leaders made a commitment to double their aid to Africa by 2010. They also agreed to increase their total ODA to Africa annually to the tune of \$25 billion.⁴ On the debt issue, they made a commitment to cancel one hundred percent of the outstanding debt of qualified HIPC's to the International Monetary Fund, the International Development Association, and the African Development Fund and to provide additional resources to ensure that the financial capacity of these institutions is not jeopardized.⁵

They also reaffirmed their commitment to the Paris Declaration and renewed their pledge to help Africa prevent and resolve conflicts, promote good governance, boost investments in health infrastructure, build capacity, and stimulate growth.⁶ Despite these bold steps, there is increasing fear and concern in Africa that very little or negligible progress has been recorded in the six core areas.⁷ This concern captured the attention of the General Assembly of the United Nations in 2007 in which it asserted that if the current trend continues, African states will not be able to mobilize the needed resources to finance public investment critical to achieving the MDGs. To address this trend, the General Assembly held a High-level Dialogue on Financing for Development in 2007, followed by an international conference in Doha to review the implementation of the Monterrey Consensus.⁸

Based on this background, this study assesses the level of progress made in Africa in the six core areas of the Consensus to determine the extent to which the continent's goals have been achieved. To achieve the goal of this paper, the twenty-two-year annual data on key macroeconomic indices were assessed.

Growth Indicators in Africa before and after the MC

It is safe to argue that some African states have made relative progress in economic growth since the adoption of the Monterrey Consensus in 2002. For instance, the annual growth rate of real gross domestic product (GDP) increased from 3.39 percent in the pre-Monterrey period to 4.82% in the post-Monterrey period from 2002 to 2020 in sub-Saharan Africa. It is also expected that the economic performance of the region will improve in the coming years. For instance, estimates between 2007 and 2022 showed that the GDP of Africa grows at an annual rate of 7.69%.⁹

Growth performance varies across Africa's sub-regions, as North and East Africa recorded higher growth rates than other sub-regions. The average annual growth in North Africa was 7.69% in the post-Monterrey period. Economic growth in the Democratic Republic of Congo, Tanzania, Kenya, and Ethiopia made East and Central Africa the second and third fastest growing sub-regions in the post-Montreal period, respectively. The Southern Africa sub-region also made significant progress, improving its growth rate from an average of 3.34% in the

³Clero Dupasquier and Patrick Osakwe, "Trade capacity building in sub-Saharan Africa: emerging issues and challenges," In D. N. Dinello and E. Aryeetey, A. (2007). Testing global interdependence: issues on trade, aid, migration and development. Cheltenham: Edward Elgar Publishing, 2007, p. 16.

⁴G. Dijkstra and N. Hermes, "The Uncertainty of Debt Service Payment and Economic Growth of Highly Indebted Poor Countries," Manuscript, Helsinki: United Nations University, 2001, p. 106.

⁵Karjomuise, Osakwe, Shimeles and Verick, *The Monterrey Consensus...*, 2007, p. 19.

⁶B. Clements, R. Bhattacharya and T. Nguyen (Eds.) "Can Debt Relief Boost Growth in Low-Income Countries

⁷See Peter Nunnenkamp and Rainer Thiele, "Financing for development: The gap between words and deeds since Monterrey," Kiel Working Paper, No. 1691, Kiel Institute for the World Economy (IfW), Kiel, 2011.

⁸P. Collier and S. O'Connell, "Opportunities, Choices and Syndromes," Paper presented at the AERC/Harvard Workshop on Explaining African Economic Growth, Weather head Center, New York, 2005, p. 18.

⁹N. Ndulu and O'Connell, Gover

pre-Monterrey period to 5.62% in the post-Monterrey period, representing the highest percentage point increase in growth experienced in the African region during the period under review. The Angolan economy's recovery contributed to this growth.

African states have also improved in other areas of economic performance, such as macroeconomic stability. To achieve this, African states must deal with their vulnerability to internal and external shocks, the effects of which linger for a long period. Political instability, drought, flood, epidemics, and terms of trade shocks are some factors that stunt growth and development in Africa. To address this, African states must put in place mechanisms to prevent and resolve political conflicts and protect their economies from external shocks by diversifying their production and exporting earnings. They must also ensure that the increase in growth is translated into social development. Given the strong link between education, health, and poverty, African states must ensure that much is done to lift people out of poverty to stimulate and maintain stable economic development.¹⁰

Highlighting the Monterrey Consensus

Mobilizing Domestic Financial Resources to Promote Economic Development

Domestic savings is one of the means of mobilizing domestic financial resources. It is necessary to provide resources for investments, boost financial market development, and stimulate economic growth. However, African states hardly mobilize enough domestic resources to meet their investment needs. This explains the continual financing gaps in African states. Records indicate that since the adoption of the Monterrey Consensus, African states have made very little progress in this direction. Based on the average annual data, the ratio of savings to GDP increased from 22% in the pre-Monterrey period to 26% in the post-Monterrey period. In 2007, the average ratio increased to 29%. However, domestic investment as a share of the GDP has been slow in both the pre- and post-Monterrey periods.¹¹

The state is an important means of domestic savings because of its capacity to mobilize resources through taxation. An increase in public sector savings increases the state's ability to provide and maintain social services, such as education, health, infrastructure, portable water, and other social amenities that are necessary for the realization of long-term development objectives. Available data show that Sub-Saharan Africa has made little progress in the area of government revenue to GDP, both in the pre- and post-Monterrey period. However, Angola, Botswana, Eritrea, Gabon, Lesotho, Namibia, and the Seychelles recorded a high revenue ratio during the period under review. Despite this relative growth, some African states still have a very low tax ratio, which explains the low aggregate figure in these states.¹²

History has shown that private savings play a crucial role in Africa's economic development, although the long-term trend of private savings has not been encouraging. Low per capita income levels and high dependency on foreign aid have led to a lower rate of private savings. Furthermore, existing financial institutions do not help in mobilizing domestic resources. Thus, micro-finance institutions play a role in the mobilization of domestic resources. The emergence of micro-finance banks in many African states has created opportunities for small-scale entrepreneurs to access credit facilities for business development and employment generation.

¹⁰J. Elbadwi and F. Mwea, "Can Africa's Saving Collapse be Reversed?" *World Bank Economic Review*, Vol. 4, No. 3, 2003, p. 76.

¹¹Karjomuise, Osakwe, Shimeless and Verick, *Te Monterrey Consensus ...*, 2007, p. 22.

¹²World Economic and Financial Survey Series, IMF, Washington, DC, 2007, p. 56.

Strengthening the capacity and operational approach of these micro-finance institutions could accelerate the pace of financial sector development and poverty reduction.¹³

The Monterrey Consensus recognized the relevance of good governance in the mobilization of domestic resources because weak and inefficient public institutions reduce domestic savings, especially in the area of corruption. For African states to scale up their saving ratios to enhance prospects for the realization of SDGs, governments must create an investment environment conducive for the organized private sector to have an incentive to access existing domestic savings for investment. More effort is needed to improve the investment environment to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals.¹⁴

Mobilizing International Development Resources

FDI is globally recognized as a vital complement to domestic resources with the potential to facilitate economic development. It more strongly promotes productivity and income growth than domestic investment.¹⁵ FDI enhances technology transfer, generates employment, improves competitiveness, and boosts exports. However, in Africa, the flow of FDI is low. With the adoption of the Monterrey Consensus, African states have made little progress in attracting foreign direct investment (FDI). In 2006, Africa attracted 39 billion dollars (\$39 billion) in gross FDI inflows compared to 12 billion dollars (\$12 billion) recorded between 1998 and 2001. For Sub-Saharan Africa, net FDI inflows jumped from nine billion, seven hundred million dollars (\$9.7 billion) to 13 billion, four hundred million dollars (\$13.4 billion) between 2001 and 2006.¹⁶ Despite these improvements in FDI flow, its share in African GDP is minimal. In the pre-Monterrey period, it was 2.1% but rose to 2.4% in the post-Monterrey period. This rise aligns with the objective of the Monterrey Consensus, which explicitly refers to the least developed countries as those groups most in need of FDI to achieve national development priorities.¹⁷

Globalization of the capitalist economy has increased competition for FDI, and states like China and India have become major players in this area. Consequently, African states must prepare for this competition for FDI by improving their infrastructure, reducing political risk, enhancing macroeconomic stability, diversifying export base, and utilizing gains for regional integration as an effective tool for promoting trade and investment.¹⁸ Furthermore, African states should place a high premium on the boosting of intra-African FDI and create incentives for the private sector to invest in the region to curb capital flight. So far, only South Africa has benefited from intra-African FDI flows. Bearing in mind the relevance of FDI to economic development, African states should be cautious and selective in the types of FDI inflow they seek to attract. FDI that encourages technology transfer and local capacity building is preferred. More so, African states should pay attention to sectors that have high value, employment generation potential, and environmental impact, and FDI should be given serious consideration.¹⁹

¹³ World Economic and Financial Survey Series, IMF, Washington, DC, 2007, p. 56.

¹⁴ Regional Economic Outlook: Sub-Saharan Africa, IMF, Washington, DC, 2007, p. 101.

¹⁵ OECD, *Foreign Direct Investment for Development: Maximizing Benefits, Minimizing, Costs*. Paris, 2002.

¹⁶ Karjomuise, Osakwe, Shimeless and Verick, *The Monterrey Consensus ...*, 2007, p. 27.

¹⁷ Peter Nunnekenkamp and Rainer Thiele, "Financing for Development: The Gap between Words and Deeds since Monterrey", Kiel Working Paper, No. 1691, Kiel Institute for the World Economic (IfW), Kiel, 2011, p. 15.

¹⁸ The Emerging Landscape of FDI: Some Salient Issues, UNCTAD, Geneva, 2007, p. 33.

¹⁹ Dupasquier and Osakwe, *Trade Capacity Building in Sub-Saharan Africa*, p. 19 (2007)

All said, there has been a slight increase in private capital flows to some African states since the Monterrey Consensus was adopted. Private capital flow moved from 13 billion, four hundred million (\$13.4 billion) in the pre-Monterrey period to 19 billion dollars (\$19 billion) in the post-Monterrey period.²⁰ Some of the capital flows are in the form of equity capital. Moreover, remittances have played an important role in financing development in the region, and more of these will have an impact on the continent's economic development.²¹

Promotion of International Trade (Aid-for-Trade)

International trade, or in the context of the Monterrey Consensus, aid-for-trade, is one of the important means for growth and any effort aimed at accelerating development courtesy of international trade, a state can have access to foreign exchange, expand its market, increase FDI, facilitate transfer of technology, and boost domestic productivity. It aims, among other things, to provide support for the productive capacities of the poor, to connect the poor to markets through a set of marketing policies, institutions, and investments in rural infrastructure, and to facilitate adjustment to trade-induced structural change.²²

It can also generate employment and increase domestic income, as it is obvious that African states record a very low share of global trade. Reversing this ugly trend and incorporating Africa into the world capitalist system have been the goals of African states and their development partners. The Monterrey Consensus placed importance on international trade in accelerating economic development and integrating African states into the multilateral market system.²³

In the pre-Monterrey period, export trade growth increased from 4.7% to 6% in the post-Monterrey period. Despite this increase, African states' export growth is relatively low, facing stiff competition in the global market for its export, perpetuating its marginalization in the international capitalist economy. Furthermore, most African states face serious internal and external barriers to trade and export market expansion and are unable to receive a fair share of the benefits from the multilateral trading system. The Doha Development Agenda was meant to address this issue, but it had little or no benefit for Africa.²⁴ With low elasticity of demand, African states continued to be the net exporter of primary commodities, hence little or no opportunity for export market expansion. The diversification of production and export in global trade is a sine qua non-for Africa to increase its share of global exports. It will also protect African states from external shocks of trade fluctuations. Export diversification will also improve productive capacities.

To achieve this, African states must maintain stable macroeconomic conditions, create regulatory measures for export promotion, ginger the private sector, and develop institutional infrastructure. Achieving diversification in export requires adequate human and financial resources, which are not enough at the disposal of African states. To address this inadequacy, the development partners of African states play a critical role to play. These include having market access opportunities; countries in the global North should offer duty-free and quota-free African exports into their large markets. This will create an incentive for African states to diversify their export structure to take advantage of improved market access and rapidly engender their integration into the world capitalist

²⁰ E. R. Borensztein, J. De Gregorio and J. W. Lee How Does Foreign Direct Investment Affect Economic Growth? *Journal of International Economics*, 45(1), 1998, pp. 115-135, 1998.

²¹ Karjomuise, Osakwe, Shimeless and Verick, *Monterrey Consensus*, 2007, p. 29.

²² Nunnenkamp, P., & Thiele, "Financing for development: The gap between words and deeds since Monterrey", Kiel Working Paper, 1691. Kiel Institute for the World Economy (IfW), Kiel, 2011.

²³ Karjomuise, Osakwe, Shimeless and Verick, *Monterrey Consensus*, 2007, p. 30.

²⁴ N. Ndulu, N., & O'Connell, S. (1998). *Governance and Growth in Sub-Saharan Africa*, 1998, p. 78.

system.²⁵ Second, states in the global North can help by increasing their financial support for infrastructure development in states of the global South. To this end, the development partners of African states should provide more support for regional infrastructure development projects to reduce transportation costs and provide capacity building support in the field of trade and export development in other areas where the development partners can help African states diversify their economy. Such support will encourage these countries to bridge the gap between resource needs and availability and put them in a competitive position in world capitalist markets. To achieve this, all must be involved in the initiative to fast track the necessary measures toward the realization of this objective.²⁶

The Aid-for-Trade Initiative must avoid the problems associated with past trade capacity building programs such as the lack of ownership of these programs by the recipient states, the focus on donor priorities against those in the receiving state and the lack of adequate funding. Moreover, there should be donor support for trade and export market development among African states. The effect of this support will be used if African states put in more effort to fully mainstream trade into their national development strategies. This requires involving all relevant stakeholders in the formulation and implementation of trade policies to ensure that macroeconomic and social policies complement each other, address impediments to market access, and strengthen trade capacity.

Increased international financial and technical cooperation

One of the six pillars of the Monterrey Consensus is to increase international financial and technical cooperation between African states and their development partners. The Monterrey Consensus places a high priority on the role of ODA as a complement to other sources of financing in developing states. It also emphasizes that a substantial increase in ODA is a vital need of these developing states if they are to achieve their development goals. Since the adoption of the Monterrey Consensus, development partners have made several promises to scale up the quantity and efficacy of aid in these developing nations.²⁷ The fallout of the G8 Gleneagles Summit and the Paris Declaration reaffirmed the commitments made in the Monterrey Consensus, especially in terms of aid quantity and quality.²⁸ The remaining part of this section is devoted to a detailed analysis of the quantity and quality of aid and other innovative sources of funding to developing African states.

Elements of progress on aid quantity to developing states in Africa have been observed since the adoption of the Monterrey Consensus. Net ODA flows to Africa have increased from sixteen billion dollars in the pre-Monterrey period to 28 billion dollars in the post-Monterrey period. Nigeria is among the major recipients of aid in the post-Monterrey period because of the debt relief it obtained in 2005. Overall, 43 states in Africa experienced an increase in ODA flow in the post-Monterrey period, whereas nine countries did not experience such an increase.²⁹ A major concern of African states is that these increases in aid are due to debt relief and humanitarian assistance, but do not reflect additional resources available to finance development programs. If these two elements are removed, it is obvious that there has been no significant increase in the number of deeds to the African States.

²⁵World Economic and Financial Survey, 2007, p. 16.

²⁶The Emerging Landscape of Foreign Direct Investment, 2007, p. 35.

²⁷Nunnenkamp, P., & Thiele, "Financing for development: The gap between words and deeds since Monterrey", Kiel Working Paper, No. 1691, Kiel Institute for the World Economy (IfW), Kiel, 2011, p.5.

²⁸G. Dijkstra and N. Hermes, "The Uncertainty of Debt Service Payment and Economic Growth of Highly...

²⁹Regional Economic Outlook: Sub-Saharan Africa, IMF, Washington DC, 2007, 106.

The Monterrey Consensus also called on development partners to make more effective positive contributions to development in the recipient states. The Paris Declaration of 2005 was the first bold attempt by developed and developing states to take concrete steps to enhance aid effectiveness. The declaration provided a framework to improve the quality of aid anchored on five major pillars: ownership, alignment, harmonization, management for results, and mutual responsibility.³⁰ However, some steps were taken to monitor progress in improving the effectiveness of aid. The survey conducted by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development in 2006 arrived at the following conclusions regarding the Paris Declaration: increased awareness and promotion of dialogue at the state levels; the slowness of the donors; the need to strengthen national development strategies with respect to donor support; the management and delivery of aid by donors; the use of performance frameworks and reports by states and donors; and the development of credible monitoring systems.³¹

Some civil society groups have been effective in the assessment of the degree of progress and implementation of international commitment on aid effectiveness. One such group is the African Forum and Network in Debt Development (AFRODAD). In 2006, AFRODAD commissioned studies on Ghana, Kenya, Malawi, and Mozambique to assess the implementation of the Paris Declaration on Aid Management and donor harmonization. Based on the results of these studies, progress has been made in the areas of the international aid agenda, especially in the areas of stimulating debate on aid effectiveness in the donor and recipient states and strengthening accountability between government and citizens and donors and recipients.³² According to Torsvik, the basis for donor coordination rest on the public good character of poverty alleviation in aid recipient countries.³³

The studies confirmed that African states have taken adequate measures to strengthen leadership and ownership of their development process. Some African states have developed a comprehensive national development framework with strategic priorities linked to their medium-term expenditure framework. In some states, the PRS serves as an operational policy framework for donor support to partner countries. A state like Kenya has taken effective leadership for coordinating aid and introducing a more harmonized aligned system at the national and sector levels.

In the area of alignment, studies show that although progress has been made in aligning donor support to the national development framework of the partner country, such progress has little or no impact and has been very negligible. Most donors channeled their support to the government outside the budget system. The high concentration of donor support in proper finance limits government flexibility in the use of funds and prevents development priority. Moreover, the high percentage of flexibility in the use of funds prevents development priority. Apart from the high percentage of project finance donor support, the high unpredictability of aid flow undermines budget planning and implementation of development projects. Progress has been made in aligning donor support to the partner's public financial management and procurement system. Although donor confidence has improved in some African states, it remains weak, unaccountable, and non-transparent in some states.

³⁰Collier and O'Connell, "Opportunities, Choices and Syndrome...", 2005, p. 20.

³¹Collier and O'Connell, "Opportunities, Choices and Syndrome...", 2005, p. 20.

³²Monterrey Consensus, 2007, 31

³³G. Torsvik, Foreign economic aid: Should donors cooperate? *Journal of Development Economics*, 2005, 77(2), 503-515.

In the areas of harmonization, case studies gave mixed results, as in some states, such as Kenya, donors show stray resolve for harmonization, including joint missions, joint analytical work, and joint donor-government assessment of technical capacity building. A certain level of progress toward harmonization has been made in other states, though it has been laced with donor loss of visibility because of moving toward joint actions and fewer stand-alone projects. In states such as Malawi, Nigeria, and Mozambique, multiple and overlapping processes, mission reviews, and meetings continue to be the norm rather than the exception.³⁴

On managing for results, the studies show that human and financial capacity constraints continue to hamper efforts at managing for results. African states are yet to move toward a full result-oriented culture because of the weak and infective monitoring and evaluation mechanisms. Although donor countries have implemented certain measures to support partner countries in strengthening their monitoring and evaluation mechanisms, progress in this area is not encouraging. Owing to this ineffective means of monitoring and evaluation in the recipient states, donors continue to rely on their own monitoring and evaluation system.

In the area of mutual accountability, the study shows that although some African states have made significant progress in strengthening their accountability to donor countries, there is limited progress in strengthening their accountability to municipal constituencies such as parliaments and civil society organizations. This obviously undermines genuine ownership of the development process.³⁵

The Monterrey Consensus recognizes that ODA would not be sufficient to finance development in poor countries of the global South, such as Africa. Conscious of this inadequacy, the international community has tried to stand in the health sector. The major instruments developed in this direction are the International Financing Facility for Immunization, Aviation Levy, and AMC. This section discusses these instruments in detail.

- a. The International Finance Facility for Immunization (IFFI) was launched in 2006 as an instrument of development in the health sector with the aim of front-loading future aid commitments by borrowing from the International Financial Markets. It ensures that timely availability of resources from aid pledges for investment in health prevention and development programs. The program receives the support of France, Italy, Norway, Spain, Sweden, the United Kingdom and South Africa. This facility also provides funds to the Global Alliance for Vaccine and Immunization.
- b. Aviation Levy: This is the use of aviation tax to generate development resources. This measure received a boost after France launched its air ticket in July 2006 to raise resources to combat HIV/AIDS, malaria, and tuberculosis. Most of the resources are channeled through the United Nations International Drug Purchase Facility; 18 out of 34 African states have joined the facility.
- c. Advanced Market Commitment It was launched in February 2007 to create an incentive for pharmaceutical companies to develop vaccines for diseases common in the global South. The commitment could cover areas such as education and infrastructure with links to export capacity as well as competitiveness with the potential of contributing to poverty alleviation.³⁶

³⁴Elbadwi and Mwege, "Can Africa's Saving Collapse be Reversed?", 2003, p. 126.

³⁵World Economic and Financial Survey, 2007, p. 17.

³⁶Karjomuise, Osakwe, Shimeless and Verick, Monterrey Consensus, 2007, p. 33.

External Debt and Sustainable Development

Africa's external debt burden has remained a lingering problem in most African states in particular and the international community at large, with its negative impact on development. Huge external debt promotes increased taxes, discourages private sector investment, creates difficulties in obtaining more loans, and slows economic growth. Studies have shown that external debt has negative impacts on economic development after reaching a critical debt threshold, especially when the net present value of debt is greater than (160%) of export and (40%) of gross domestic product (GDP). The HIPC initiative of 1996 and the enhanced HIPC initiative of 1999 are the bold attempts made by the members of the international community in the pre-Monterrey period to deal with the issue of external debt militating against the developing states.³⁷ However, many states in Africa welcomed these initiatives, but they expressed concern about their implementation, especially in providing long-term solutions to their external debt burden. One of the problems of these initiatives is the criteria used to measure debt sustainability and approaches to predict debt dynamics, which do not consider the individual country's circumstances. Another important area of concern among African states is the slow progress toward decisions and completion points in the HIPC initiatives and the lack of debt relief, which has not led to an increase in the transfer of development resources.

Bearing these limitations in mind, the G8 states at their Gleneagles Summit in 2005 made another effort in line with the principles of the Monterrey Consensus by introducing the Multilateral Debt Relief Initiative (MDRI) aimed at canceling all debts owed by HIPC to the IMF, IDA, and African Development Bank (AfDB).³⁸ With these initiatives, the external debt situation has improved in recent years. In the pre-Monterrey period, Africa's annual external debt was \$274 billion, but it fell to \$244 billion in 2006. Since then, modest progress has been made in this direction. Overall, in the post-Monterrey period, African states made remarkable progress in the implementation of the MDRI introduced in 2005. It is to the credit of the Monterrey Consensus that considerable progress has been made in removing over-indebtedness as an obstacle to sustainable development.³⁹

The debt relief received by Nigerians and other countries improved the continent's economic performance.⁴⁰ However, despite the progress made since the adoption of the Monterrey Consensus, much remains undone in this direction. The major objectives of the debt relief initiative are attaining sustainable development and fast growth in poverty reduction. This is because excessive debt accumulation hampers long-term economic growth. When debt is accumulated and a country is in a difficulty of payment, the debt service tends to offset returns from previous debt invested in the domestic economy and discourage future domestic and foreign investment. Thus, debt relief is essentially meant to reverse the negative impact of debt overhang.

African states are also concerned that the debt ratio has started to fall. To speed up progress in this regard, there is a need to increase the participation of creditors in the highly indebted Paris Club Creditors. The rising profile of China and India as sources of concessional credit facilities for African states has increased the tendency of

³⁷The Emerging Landscape of FDI, pp. 39, 2007 .

³⁸Gleneagles Communiqué (2005). Climate Change, Energy and Sustainable Development. <http://www.g7.utoronto.ca/summit/2005gleneagles/communique.pdf> (Accessed April, 2021).

³⁹VENRO Sustainable Financing for Development and Poverty Eradication Policy Paper for the Second International Conference on Development Financing in Doha The Association of German Development NGOs (VENRO). Bonn. <http://www.un.org/esa/ffd/doha/VENROPolicyPaperDoha.pdf>, 2018 (Accessed: April, 2022).

⁴⁰World Economic and Financial Survey, 2007, p. 19. <https://www.wefs.org/>

more debt accumulation as new creditors have more flexible loan disbursement conditionalities. There is also the concern that resources freed through debt relief are spent on public service delivery and social service with little or nothing allocated to the manufacturing sector of the economy, which may serve as engine room for long-term growth and poverty reduction.⁴¹ Though investment in the social sector is necessary because of its multiplying effects, especially in the area of poverty alleviation, the productive sector of the economy must be given adequate attention. Furthermore, debt relief alone is not enough to ensure long-term sustainability in Africa. Other policy actions aimed at reducing external shocks, especially in the area of export and repayment capacity, should be adequately utilized. Finally, all attention should not be on the HIPC as non-HIPCs are also facing huge challenges in terms of the debt burden.

Systemic Issues

The Monterrey Consensus stressed the need for an international monetary, financial, and trading system to complement national development efforts. In this regard, it called for an improvement in the global economic governance of international institutions as well as the coordination of policy and programs by these institutions. It also called for coordination among relevant ministries and agencies to enhance coherence in policy design and formulation to ensure that these policies have the expected impact on their economies. One of the ways expected to achieve these goals is to increase the number of African states participating in the decision-making of institutions such as the International Monetary Fund, the World Bank, and the World Trade Organization. Despite their numerical strength, African states have been excluded from or insufficiently represented in international organizations that make decisions on issues that have a far-reaching impact on their economies. Since the adoption of the Monterrey Consensus, conscious efforts have been made to enhance the participation of African states in decision-making in the WTO.

At the 5th Ministerial Conference held in Cancun in 2003 and the 6th Ministerial Conference held in Hong Kong in 2005, trade ministers of most African states were selected as facilitators in key areas of the negotiations and participated in Green-room meetings where critical trade decisions were made. That was a welcome development, which led to Ngozi Okonjo-Iweala conceding the position of the Director General for the World Trade Organization to an African woman, an unprecedented feat for Africa. Regarding the World Bank and IMF, no significant attempt has been made to increase the voice of African states in decision-making. At the 2006 IMF annual meeting in Singapore in 2006, an ad hoc quota increase was approved for China, Korea, Mexico, and Turkey. This development drastically reduced the relative share of African states and, hence, their influence in fund decision-making.⁴² States in Sub-Saharan Africa account for approximately 25% of IMF membership but have a voting power of 4.4%. Obviously, the global governance of international organizations is an area in which African states should be adequately represented if the goals of the Monterrey Consensus are to be realized in the continent.

Policy coherence at the national level is also needed. It is necessary to address the problem of incoherent economic and development policies. If these policies are to contribute meaningfully to the realization of the goals of the Monterrey Consensus in African states, it is necessary that donor's policies in diverse areas, including Overseas Development Assistance, trade and market access, finance and debt, migration, and

⁴¹Dijkstra and Hermes, "The Uncertainty of Debt Service Payment and Economic Growth of Highly Indebted Poor Countries," 2001, p. 110.

⁴²*ibid.*

agriculture, are consistent with the goals of this Consensus and other internationally agreed development goals. Issues such as commodity price risk management, vulnerability to external shocks, and currency and banking crisis prevention and management must also be addressed as national systemic issues.

Prospects of the Monterrey Consensus

The economic performance of Africa has improved since the adoption of the Monterrey Consensus in 2002. However, this has not translated into poverty alleviation, economic growth, and better living conditions. Against this background, African states and their development partners must accelerate their efforts to ensure that the goals of the Consensus are realized in the region. To achieve this, serious action is required in the six core areas of the Convention, as discussed below.

African states must recognize that the mobilization of domestic resources is the most reliable and sustainable source of development finance. There is a need to take concrete action to boost savings and reduce or eliminate domestic capital flight. African states must exploit the development potential of thriving micro-finance institutions to mobilize and channel savings into productive investment. The regional integration of capital markets should also be explored as an effective way to boost the region's stock market development. Capital markets' regionalization will increase capital markets' liquidity and provide a large pool of investment resources for national and regional development. In the area of trade reforms, African states must ensure that the reforms in this area go with fiscal policy changes that would offset the loss of revenue from trade taxes.

A coherent and all-embracing policy that can attract foreign capital to complement domestic resources and external aid must be adopted by African states. Competition for foreign capital has become intense with the increasing globalization of trade and finance. Consequently, countries in Africa must improve their investment environment and develop their infrastructure to reverse their low, declining, or stagnant share in global private capital flows. However, efforts should also be made to ensure that domestic investors are not discriminated against in the drive to attract private capital flows. Furthermore, investment policies should be liberalized and harmonized within the continent to encourage cross-border investment between states. At the national level, efforts should be made to increase and improve access to financial services to make it easier for people to receive remittances from abroad through the banking system and other formal channels. Development partners should also reduce the transaction costs of remitting loans to developing countries.

Considering the fact that trade is the engine of development, development partners should create a trading environment that allows the region to unlock its export potentials, as they should offer duty- and quota-free access to exports of African states and provide more stable and adequate funding for trade capacity building programs. Moreover, progress in the implementation of the Aid-for-Trade Initiative is necessary for African states to design trade policies that are conducive to local environments. African states should also remove obstacles to export promotion, such as poor infrastructure, bureaucracy, and customs procedures that increase transaction costs. They must also diversify their production and export structures to reduce their vulnerability to external shocks and increase their share of trade benefits.

Some African states rely more on the flow of overseas development assistance to finance their investment projects. Development partners should double their efforts to meet their pledges. They should also walk their talk to untie aid flows and make them more reliable as more efforts should be made to enhance the effectiveness of aid. In addition, more donors should support innovative sources of financing, such as the International Finance Facility for Immunization, the Air Ticket Levy, and the AMC.

Much work is needed to realize the goals of the Monterrey Consensus in the area of debt relief. Although progress has been made in this direction, there is a need to extend eligibility for the debt relief program to non-highly indebted poor countries and reduce the number of years it takes for countries to move from decision to completion point. To address this, the use of the existing debt sustainability framework as a guide for assessing the risks associated with new loans is recommended.

Members of the international community must seriously consider the issue of increasing the voice of African states in decision-making bodies of international financial institutions. This will serve as a veritable means of making these institutions more democratic and sensitive to African states' needs and concerns. The WTO has set a good precedent whereby others, such as the IMF and World Bank, should borrow a leaf from the WTO, as being part of democratic processes will guarantee adequate representation of African states.⁴³

References

Borensztein, E. R., De Gregorio, J., and J.W. Lee How Does Foreign Direct Investment Affect Economic Growth? *Journal of International Economics*, 1998, 45(1).

Clements, B., Bhattacharya, R., & Nguyen, T. (Eds.), "Can Debt Relief Boost Growth in Low Income Countries"? *Economic Issues*, No. 34, 2007.

Collier, P., & O'Connell, S., "Opportunities, Choices and Syndromes", Paper presented at the AERC/Harvard Workshop on Explaining African Economic Growth. New York, 2005.

Dijkstra, G., & Hermes, N. "The Uncertainty of Debt Service Payment and Economic Growth of Highly Indebted Poor Countries," Manuscript, Helsinki: United Nations University, 2001.

Dupasquier, C., & Osakwe, P. "Trade Capacity Building in Sub-Saharan Africa: Emerging Issues and Challenges," In D. N. Dinello and E. Aryeetey, A. (Eds.), *Testing global interdependence: Issues of Trade, Aid, Migration and Development*, Cheltenham: Edward Elgar Publishing, 2007.

Elbadwi, J., & Mwege, F. "Can Africa's Saving Collapse be Reversed?" *World Bank Economic Review*, Vol.4, No.3, 2003.

Gleneagles Communique Climate Change, Energy and Sustainable Development. 2005.
<http://www.g7.utoronto.ca/summit/2005gleneagles/communique.pdf>

Karjomuise, K., Osakwe, P., Shimeles, A., & Verick, S. (Eds.). *The Monterrey Consensus and Development in Africa: Progress, Challenges and Way Forward: the UN Economic Commission for Africa*, 2007.

Ndulu, N., & O'Connell S., "Governance and growth in sub-Saharan Africa", *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 2008.

⁴³ *Ibid.*

Nunnenkamp, P., & Rainer, T. (2011) Financing for development: The gap between words and deeds since Monterrey. Kiel Working Paper, No.1691, Kiel Institute for the World Economy (IfW), Kiel, 2011.

OECD, Foreign Direct Investment for Development: Maximizing Benefits, Minimizing Costs. Paris, 2002.

Regional Economic Outlook: Sub-Saharan Africa, IMF, Washington, DC, 2007.

The Emerging Landscape of FDI: Some Salient Issues, Geneva: UNCTAD, 2007.

Torsvik, G. "Foreign Economic Aid: Should Donors Cooperate?" *Journal of Development Economics*, 77 (2), 2005.

United Nations (UN) Financing for Development The Monterrey Consensus of the International Conference on Financing for Development. <http://www.un.org/esa/ffd/monterrey/MonterreyConsensus.pdf>, 2003). (Accessed: April, 2021).

VENRO Sustainable Financing for Development and Poverty Eradication Policy Paper for the Second International Conference on Development Financing in Doha Bonn: Association of German Development NGOs (VENRO). <http://www.un.org/esa/ffd/doha/VENROPolicyPaperDoha.pdf>, 2008.

World Economic and Financial Survey Series, IMF, Washington, DC 2007.